

Supporting Information for

Observed climate change impacts on plant communities in Mediterranean-type ecosystems: A systematic review

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Datasets S1 to S5 (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15008893](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15008893))

Supporting Information Text

Methods

Search terms — An initial broad scoping search was done in both Web of Science and Scopus to identify any terms that were too broad to include as single terms. Where an individual word yielded over 10 000 results on its own, it was adjusted to form a string or phrase contained in quotation marks, which helped narrow down the search. For example, searching “scrub” in Web of Science yielded 13 458 results, which suggested that the term was too general, with too many potential definitions as both a verb and multiple nouns. In contrast, searching “coastal scrub”, referring to a specific vegetation type, yielded 124 results. The limited success of using broad phrases such as “plant community” identified the need to include more specific descriptive terms for the vegetation of MTE regions, often in non-English languages. Furthermore, making use of the Boolean operator ‘OR’ when including these vegetation descriptors, as well as when applying synonyms for concepts that are used interchangeably in the literature (e.g. “climate change” OR “global warming”) facilitated capturing a broader range of results, while using the ‘AND’ operator allowed greater refinement of key terms that were necessary for a relevant search result.

Data formatting — After combining the exported datasets from Web of Science and Scopus and ensuring that the same data were reflected under the same headings, only specific data columns were retained for further analysis: publication title, authors, year of publication, volume, issue, source title (i.e. journal name), DOI, keywords, and abstract text. All publication titles were transformed to lowercase to ensure uniformity of the data, since the export contained some titles in uppercase and some in title case (initial caps), which would interfere with deduplication. Deduplication was then performed on titles only.

Literature screening — Phase I of the screening process was a rapid assessment of publication titles to check conformity to the PECO statement, involving one reviewer. Phase II involved screening of titles and abstracts by two reviewers. Any uncertainty in reviewer decisions were discussed among the authors, and final decisions were reached by consensus and expert opinion, based strictly on the predetermined eligibility criteria. For example, several publications used terms like “even-aged stands” or “single-species stands” to describe a vegetation system which the authors had identified as a ‘forest’, though by definition these systems should be referred to as ‘plantations’. When understood in this way, it meant that the study met one of the explicit exclusion criteria (i.e. exclude studies pertaining to pastoral/agricultural systems, croplands, plantations or urban environments), therefore clarifying the review decision to exclude the study. Any articles cited in the IPCC WGII AR5 Chapter 4 and AR6 Chapter 2 in reference to MTEs that did not appear in the initial inclusion list were subsequently included in the combined corpus of literature for the final screening phase. Phase III of the screening process involved

retrieval and review of publication full-texts. Where full-texts were not available or could not be retrieved from online sources, the item was not considered for further review or analysis. One reviewer read all publication full-texts to confirm that the predetermined eligibility criteria were met.

Fig. S1. Full systematic review workflow.

Fig. S2. Number of publications by region relating to climate change impacts on plant communities in Mediterranean-type ecosystems over time.

Table S1. Metadata for data extraction questionnaire performed via Google Forms.

Category	Question	Input type	Description of input	Input options
1. Bibliographic information	Title	<i>Long answer text</i>	<i>Title of publication</i>	
	Year	<i>Short answer text</i>	<i>Year of publication</i>	
	DOI	<i>Short answer text</i>	<i>DOI of publication</i>	
	Citation	<i>Long answer text</i>	<i>Bibliographic citation for publication</i>	
2. Study design	Listed research questions / aims	<i>Long answer text</i>	<i>Research questions and/or aims as listed in the publication</i>	
	Listed hypotheses / expectations	<i>Long answer text</i>	<i>Hypotheses and/or expectations as listed in the publication</i>	

Sampling frequency *Checkboxes* *Frequency of sampling as detailed in the Methods section or Supplementary Information, in short form*

- Once-off;
- Once a year, twice;
- Once a year, multiple times;
- Multiple times a year, over a period;
- Once a year, long-term (>10 years);
- Infrequently, long-term (>10 years)

More details on sampling frequency *Long answer text* *e.g. March - April annually for 3 years; Twice during the growing season for 3 years; [...]*

Study design *Long answer text* *Description of data collection and processing methods*

Line(s) of evidence *Checkboxes*

- Plant-level measurements;
- Plot-level surveys;
- Remote sensing;
- Aerial/ground repeat photography;
- Citizen science;
- Other

	More details on line(s) of evidence	<i>Long answer text</i>	<i>e.g. Plot-level surveys - 1 x 1 m quadrats; Remote sensing - MODIS derived NDVI; [...]</i>	
3. Study system	Veg system ID(s)	<i>Long answer text</i>	<i>e.g. Fynbos; chaparral; kwongan; temperate coniferous forest; [...]</i>	
	Geographic region(s)	<i>Checkboxes</i>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● California, USA; ● Cape Floristic Region, South Africa; ● Central Chile; ● Mediterranean Basin; ● South and/or Southwestern Australia
	Specific country/region	<i>Long answer text</i>	<i>e.g. South Africa; Doñana National Park; [...]</i>	
	Coordinates for study sites (if provided)	<i>Long answer text</i>		
	Relevant environmental info (if provided)	<i>Long answer text</i>		

4. Observations and results	Level of grouping	Checkboxes		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Vegetation type; ● Whole community; ● Functional groups/types; ● Multiple species; ● Few species; ● Single species; ● Other
	Growth forms examined	Checkboxes		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Trees; ● Shrubs; ● Graminoids; ● Herbs/forbs; ● Other
	Total numbers of species and/or functional groups	Long answer text		
	More detail on groupings	Long answer text	<i>e.g. Ericaceae; Erica junonia; coniferous trees, [...]</i>	
	Disturbance event reported?	Multiple choice		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Yes; ● No; ● Multiple
	Nature of event(s) / disturbance	Checkboxes		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Climatic variation; ● Drought; ● Fire; ● Pathogen/Insect outbreak; ● Herbivory; ● Anthropogenic;

More detail on nature of disturbance (if reported)

Long answer text

Duration of disturbance (if reported)

Long answer text

Response variables measured

Checkboxes

- Other

- Presence: Plant;
- Presence: Pathogen;
- Mortality;
- Biomass;
- Morphometrics;
- Demographics;
- Productivity;
- Reproduction;
- Diversity;
- Metric of community / association;
- Invasion: Plant;
- Other

More details on response variables measured

Long answer text

e.g. Diversity - species counts, visual estimates of abundance, canopy diameter; Biomass - canopy area, leaf area index; Invasion - count of IAPs per plot; [...]

	Description of response(s)	<i>Long answer text</i>
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Confidence Index Assessment

To accommodate several criteria included in critical appraisal tools for environmental evidence, the original confidence index (hereafter C-index) table as recommended by O'Connor et al. (1) has been adapted to suit the purposes of this review (Table S2). While this method is usually applied to individual biological observations, we applied it at the publication level, in lieu of a conventional risk of bias assessment. We found that the points/questions that appear in the C-index framework largely overlapped with the questions appearing among the different criteria in a critical appraisal tool recommended for reviews of environmental evidence (2). Where there was no overlap, an additional point/question was generated and included in our adapted version of the C-index framework to account for other risk of bias criteria. Modifications include the following, each awarding an additional 0 or 1 point: (i) 'Variables' subsection under section (b) Data (SD), to account for risk of bias in data collection (included in Detection score); (ii) question under section (c) Quantitative analysis (SQ) to confirm whether or not the methods applied were appropriate to answer the research question (included in Detection score); (iii) addition of a new section (d) Reporting (SR) to account for clarity and completeness in reporting of results (included in Understanding score). These modifications are marked in the table with an asterisk (*). Using the C-index framework to appraise the publications included in our review also allowed us to analyse the C-index scores and draw informed conclusions about which responses were associated with high confidence, and in which regions these publications are focused.

Table S2. Modified confidence index (C-index) table.

Detection (D)	Understanding (U)	Score breakdown
(a) Expectations (SE)		<i>[Max = 6]</i>
	(i) 0 = no clear prior expectation stated	Max = 2
	+2 = prior expectation is clearly stated	

(ii) +2 = study invokes specific evidence to support prior expectation Max = 2

(iii) +1 = prior expectations are based on multiple lines of evidence Max = 1

(iv) +1 = prior expectations for alternative causal factors are articulated or confounding factors are discounted Max = 1

(b) Data (SD)

[Max = 7]

Temporal

(i) 0 = ≤10 years of data Max = 2

+1 = 11–25 years of data

+2 = >25 years of data

+1 = data spans > 30 years Max = 1

(ii) +1 = continuous data (annual) Max = 1

Spatial

(iii) 0 = single site study

Max = 1

+1 = multiple site study

(iv) 0 = local ($\leq 1000 \text{ km}^2$)

Max = 1

+1 = regional ($> 1000 \text{ km}^2$)

+1 = broad scale ($> 100,000 \text{ km}^2$)

***Variables**

*(v) +1 = response variables clearly defined and measured appropriately

Max = 1

(c) Quantitative analysis (SQ)

[Max = 7]

(i) +1 = biological trend was statistically tested to distinguish from no trend

Max = 1

(ii) +1 = a trend in a climatic variable was statistically tested to distinguish from no trend

Max = 1

(iii) +1 = temporal/spatial autocorrelations have been considered

Max = 1

*(iv) +1 = methods for testing trends were appropriate

Max = 1

(v) +2 = relationship between biological variable and climatic variable was statistically tested

Max = 2

(vi) +1 = alternative causal factors tested

Max = 1

***(d) Reporting (SR)**

[Max = 1]

*(i) +1 = reports on all considered relationships between biological and climatic variables

Max = 1

[Max (D) = 11]

[Max (U) = 10]

[Overall max = 21]

Table S3. Comparison of the C-index framework (1) with the CEECAT environmental evidence critical appraisal tool v.0.3. (2).

CEECAT criteria	CEECAT category	CEECAT checklist questions	C-index complements
Criterion 1: Risk of confounding biases	General (please answer)	1.1. Is it possible for the impact of the exposure or the effectiveness of the intervention to be confounded in this study?	Accounted for by (a) Expectations (SE) (iv) +1 = prior expectations for alternative causal factors are articulated or confounding factors are discounted
	Conditional (answer if Y/SY to 1.1, otherwise select 'Not applicable')	1.2. Did the author(s) control for all the potential confounders?	Accounted for by (a) Expectations (SE) (iv) +1 = prior expectations for alternative causal factors are articulated or confounding factors are discounted
	Conditional (answer if N/SN/Unclear to 1.2, otherwise select 'Not applicable')	1.3. Is there any justifiable reason for not controlling for all the potential confounders (so that omission of some of the potential confounders is unlikely to influence the assessment of the effectiveness or impact)?	Accounted for by (a) Expectations (SE) (iv) +1 = prior expectations for alternative causal factors are articulated or confounding factors are discounted AND (c) Quantitative analysis (SQ) (v) +1 = alternative causal factors tested
	Conditional (answer if Y/SY to 1.2 or 1.3, otherwise select 'Not applicable')	1.4. Were the potential confounders, that were controlled for, (and/or the instrumental variable used if applicable) likely to be measured accurately and precisely enough?	Accounted for by (a) Expectations (SE) (iv) +1 = prior expectations for alternative causal factors are articulated or confounding factors are discounted AND (c) Quantitative analysis (SQ) (v) +1 = alternative causal factors tested

	<p>Conditional (answer if you have answered 1.4, otherwise select 'Not applicable')</p> <p>Optional (It is suggested that detailed rationale or empirical evidence be provided when predicting magnitude and direction of bias. Assessors may skip this optional checklist question if they feel unfeasible)</p>	<p>1.5. Did the author(s) analyse the effect appropriately by taking into account the potential confounders, as well as the issue of accuracy and precision of the measurements of the potential confounders (and the instrumental variable if applicable)?</p> <p>1.6. What are the predicted magnitude and the direction of bias due to confounding?</p>	<p>Accounted for by (a) Expectations (SE) (iv) +1 = prior expectations for alternative causal factors are articulated or confounding factors are discounted AND (c) Quantitative analysis (SQ) (v) +1 = alternative causal factors tested</p> <p>N/A</p>
<p>Criterion 2: Risk of post-intervention / exposure selection biases</p>	<p>General (please answer whichever suitable)</p>	<p>2.1.a. Was the selection of subjects or areas after intervention or exposure random or systematic (i.e., based on random or systematic sampling), and exchangeability between groups could be assumed based on the selection approach?</p> <p>OR</p> <p>2.1.b. Was the entire (or nearly entire) population of inference followed-up after intervention or exposure, and exchangeability between</p>	<p>Accounted for (in part) by (b) Data (SD) (i) 0 = ≤10 years of data, +1 = 11–25 years of data, +2 = >25 years of data, +1 = data spans > 30 years, AND (ii) +1 = continuous data (annual)</p>

	before and after groups could be assumed?	
General (please answer)	2.2. Was/were the researcher(s) unaware (or blinded) of the selection of subjects or areas?	N/A
General (please answer)	2.3. After the start of the intervention/exposure or during the analysis, were any subjects or areas excluded or lost from the study or analysis?	Accounted for (in part) by (b) Data (SD) (iii) 0 = single site study, +1 = multiple site study, AND (iv) 0 = local (≤ 1000 km ²), +1 = regional (> 1000 km ²), +1 = broad scale ($> 100,000$ km ²)
Conditional (answer if N/SN/Unclear to 2.1, or Y/SY/Unclear to 2.3, otherwise select 'Not applicable')	2.4. Were the subjects or areas included in the study (or analysis) comparable between groups and so they allowed a valid comparison to be made (i.e., exchangeability or conditional exchangeability between groups could be assumed)?	Accounted for (in part) by (b) Data (SD) (iii) 0 = single site study, +1 = multiple site study, AND (iv) 0 = local (≤ 1000 km ²), +1 = regional (> 1000 km ²), +1 = broad scale ($> 100,000$ km ²)
Conditional (answer if N/SN/Unclear to 2.4, otherwise select 'Not applicable')	2.5. Were the difference(s) between groups likely to be explained by the intervention/exposure or a variable influenced by the intervention/exposure (including the outcome)?	Accounted for by (a) Expectations (SE) (iv) +1 = prior expectations for alternative causal factors are articulated or confounding factors are discounted AND (c) Quantitative analysis (SQ) (v) +1 = alternative causal factors tested

	<p>Conditional (answer if Y/SY/Unclear to 2.5, otherwise select 'Not applicable')</p> <p>Optional (It is suggested that detailed rationale or empirical evidence be provided when predicting magnitude and direction of bias. Assessors may skip this optional checklist question if they feel unfeasible)</p>	<p>2.6. Did the author(s) adjust for the potential post-intervention/exposure selection bias in an appropriate way?</p> <p>2.7. What are the predicted magnitude and the direction of bias arising from systematic differences in the selection of subjects or areas into the study or analysis after intervention or exposure?</p>	<p>N/A</p> <p>N/A</p>
<p>Criterion 3: Risk of misclassified comparison biases (observational studies only)</p>	<p>Conditional (answer if type of the study is observational, otherwise select 'not applicable')</p> <p>Conditional (answer if type of the study is observational, otherwise select 'not applicable')</p> <p>Conditional (answer if type of the study is observational, otherwise select 'not applicable')</p>	<p>3.1. Were the intervention or exposure (group) and the comparator (group) of interest sufficiently well-defined so that no meaningful vagueness remains for the intended assessment of causal effect of interest?</p> <p>3.2. Were the observed intervention or exposure (group) and the comparator (group) appropriate for the intended assessment of causal effect (i.e., causal effect of interest)?</p> <p>3.3. Might measure or classification of the observed exposure, intervention or comparator (group) have been incorrect due to error or influence of some</p>	<p>Added to C-index as (b) Data (Sd) Variables (v) 0 = response variables not clearly defined, +1 = response variables clearly defined and measured appropriately</p> <p>Added to C-index as (b) Data (Sd) Variables (v) 0 = response variables not clearly defined, +1 = response variables clearly defined and measured appropriately</p> <p>Added to C-index as (b) Data (Sd) Variables (v) 0 = response variables not clearly defined, +1 = response variables clearly defined and measured appropriately</p>

	<p>Optional (It is suggested that detailed rationale or empirical evidence be provided when predicting magnitude and direction of bias. Assessors may skip this optional checklist question if they feel unfeasible. Select 'not applicable' if experimental treatments are applied)</p>	<p>knowledge, experience or desire?</p> <p>3.4. What are the predicted magnitude and the direction of bias arising from misclassification or measurement of intervention, exposure and/or comparator?</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Criterion 4: Risk of performance biases (experimental studies only)</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Criterion 5: Risk of detection biases</p>	<p>General (please answer)</p> <p>General (please answer)</p>	<p>5.1. Was there any way for the outcome measure to be affected by knowledge of the exposure, intervention, subjects or areas, or desire for certain outcome?</p> <p>5.2. Was the measured outcome appropriate for the intended assessment of causal effect (i.e., causal effect of interest)?</p>	<p>Accounted for by (a) Expectations (SE) (iv) +1 = prior expectations for alternative causal factors are articulated or confounding factors are discounted AND (c) Quantitative analysis (SQ) (v) +1 = alternative causal factors tested</p> <p>Added to C-index as (b) Data (Sd) Variables (v) 0 = response variables not clearly defined, +1 = response variables clearly defined and measured appropriately</p>

	General (please answer)	5.3. Were the methods for measuring the outcome data the same across the groups?	Added to C-index as (b) Data (Sd) Variables (v) 0 = response variables not clearly defined, +1 = response variables clearly defined and measured appropriately
	Conditional (answer if N/SN/Unclear to 5.3)	5.4. Were the potential differences in measured outcomes between groups investigated and adjusted/corrected if necessary?	Added to C-index as (b) Data (Sd) Variables (v) 0 = response variables not clearly defined, +1 = response variables clearly defined and measured appropriately
	Optional (It is suggested that detailed rationale or empirical evidence be provided when predicting magnitude and direction of bias. Assessors may skip this optional checklist question if they feel unfeasible)	5.4. What are the predicted magnitude and the direction of bias arising from systematic differences in measurement of outcomes?	N/A
Criterion 6: Risk of outcome reporting biases	General (please answer)	6.1. Are the reported relevant outcome data (or effect estimate) likely to be of (or based on) selected measurements of the outcome?	Added to C-index as (d) Reporting (Sr) (i) +1 = reports on all considered relationships between biological and climatic variables
	General (please answer)	6.2. Are relevant outcome data likely to be unreported for some subgroup(s)?	Added to C-index as (d) Reporting (Sr) (i) +1 = reports on all considered relationships between biological and climatic variables

	<p>General (please answer)</p> <p>Optional (It is suggested that detailed rationale or empirical evidence be provided when predicting magnitude and direction of bias. Assessors may skip this optional checklist question if they feel unfeasible)</p>	<p>6.3. Is/are the analysis/analyses of the causal relationship of interest (intervention-outcome or exposure-outcome) likely to be partially reported?</p> <p>6.4. What are the predicted magnitude and the direction of bias in reporting of study findings?</p>	<p>Added to C-index as (d) Reporting (Sr) (i) +1 = reports on all considered relationships between biological and climatic variables</p> <p>N/A</p>
<p>Criterion 7: Risk of outcome assessment biases</p>	<p>General (please answer)</p> <p>General (please answer)</p> <p>Conditional (answer if inferential statistics are applied, otherwise select 'not applicable')</p>	<p>7.1. Was/were the person(s), who estimated the effectiveness of the intervention or the impact of the exposure, aware of the exposure or intervention received by subjects or areas?</p> <p>7.2. Is it likely that there is/are error(s) or inappropriate methods in the applied descriptive statistical analyses?</p> <p>7.3. Is it likely that there is/are error(s) in the applied inferential statistics (including null hypothesis testing, estimation, coding)?</p>	<p>N/A</p> <p>Added to C-index as (c) Quantitative analysis (Sq) (vi) +1 = methods for testing trends were appropriate</p> <p>Added to C-index as (c) Quantitative analysis (Sq) (vi) +1 = methods for testing trends were appropriate</p>

Conditional (answer if inferential statistics are applied, otherwise select 'not applicable')

Optional (It is suggested that detailed rationale or empirical evidence be provided when predicting magnitude and direction of bias. Assessors may skip this optional checklist question if they feel unfeasible)

7.4. Were assumptions for the applied inferential statistics violated or the applied inferential statistical methods inappropriate for the inferential goal(s)?

Added to C-index as (c) Quantitative analysis (Sq) (vi) +1 = methods for testing trends were appropriate

7.5. What are the predicted magnitude and the direction of bias due to error in applied statistical methods?

N/A

Table S4. Description of biological response categories as they appear in the data extraction questionnaire (Table S1) and examples of associated response variables from selected publications.

Response category	Type of response(s)	Examples of response variables measured
Condition	Mortality; Presence of pathogen/insect outbreak; Plant invasion	<p data-bbox="826 646 1198 678"><i>From Navarro-Cerrillo et al. (2022):</i></p> <p data-bbox="826 720 1338 953">Presence of pathogen/insect outbreak: presence of fungi (<i>Armillaria mellea</i>) and insects (<i>Cryphalus numidicus</i>, <i>Dioryctria auloi</i>), pest severity (number of trees damaged by major pathogens or pests); Mortality: level of crown defoliation</p> <p data-bbox="826 1073 1122 1104"><i>From Slingsby et al. (2017):</i></p> <p data-bbox="826 1146 1195 1178">Plant invasion: alien plant density</p>
Diversity	Diversity; Plant presence; Metric of community/association	<p data-bbox="826 1276 1143 1308"><i>From Lamprecht et al. (2021):</i></p> <p data-bbox="826 1350 1243 1419">Diversity: species richness, number of colonisation / disappearance events</p> <p data-bbox="826 1539 1170 1570"><i>From Diaz-Borrego et al. (2024):</i></p> <p data-bbox="826 1612 1268 1680">Metric of community/association: plant interaction (facilitation, inhibition, neutral)</p>

Growth	Biomass; Metric of community/association; Demographics; Morphometrics; Plant presence; Productivity; Reproduction	<p><i>From Storey et al. (2021):</i></p> <p>Biomass: fractional shrub cover; Productivity: NDVI</p> <p><i>From Andivia et al. (2018):</i></p> <p>Biomass: longitudinal shoot growth, needle mass per area, sapling stem volume, leaf area ratio, needle mass fraction; Morphometrics: needle length, diameter at breast height; Metric of community/association: number of neighbouring saplings, distance to closest adult</p> <p><i>From Galiano et al. (2012):</i></p> <p>Demographics: stand density, number of stems; Morphometrics: diameter at breast height, height of tallest stem</p>
Phenology	Productivity; Reproduction	<p><i>From Gordo et al. (2009):</i></p> <p>Reproduction: Flowering, leaf unfolding, fruit ripening, leaf falling</p> <p><i>From Camarero et al. (2015):</i></p> <p>Productivity: shoot production, phenological stage</p>
Physiology	Productivity	<p><i>From de la Riva et al. (2017):</i></p> <p>Productivity: Leaf nitrogen concentration, leaf chlorophyll a, isotopic carbon fraction</p>

Table S5. List of all species and growth forms cited in the MTE literature.

Scientific binomial	Common name	Growth form	Family	Publication reference(s) including this species*
<i>Abies alba</i>	European silver fir	Tree	Pinaceae	14, 18, 121
<i>Abies cilicica</i>	Taurus fir	Tree	Pinaceae	118
<i>Abies concolor</i>	White fir	Tree	Pinaceae	9, 23, 27, 112
<i>Abies magnifica</i>	California red fir	Tree	Pinaceae	23
<i>Abies pinsapo</i>	Spanish fir	Tree	Pinaceae	76
<i>Allocasuarina fraseriana</i>	Fraser's sheoak	Tree	Casuarinaceae	111
<i>Arbutus menziesii</i>	Pacific madrone	Tree	Ericaceae	64
<i>Austrocedrus chilensis</i>	Chilean cedar	Tree	Cupressaceae	40
<i>Banksia grandis</i>	Giant banksia	Tree	Proteaceae	111
<i>Beilschmiedia miersii</i>	Chilean belloto	Tree	Lauraceae	40
<i>Berberis montana</i>	Barberry	Shrub	Berberidaceae	40
<i>Calluna vulgaris</i>	Common heather	Shrub	Ericaceae	84
<i>Calocedrus decurrens</i>	Incense cedar	Tree	Cupressaceae	9, 27, 112
<i>Cedrus atlantica</i>	Atlas cedar	Tree	Cupressaceae	77
<i>Cistus libanotis</i>	Rock rose	Shrub	Cistaceae	21
<i>Cneorum tricoccon</i>	Spurge olive	Shrub	Rutaceae	55
<i>Corymbia calophylla</i>	Marri	Tree	Myrtaceae	12, 66, 67, 69, 100, 111, 124
<i>Cryptocarya alba</i>	Chilean acorn	Tree	Lauraceae	40

<i>Cytisus oromediterraneus</i>	Pyrenean broom	Shrub	Fabaceae	97
<i>Erica arborea</i>	Tree heather	Shrub	Ericaceae	63
<i>Escallonia revoluta</i>		Shrub	Escalloniaceae	40
<i>Eucalyptus marginata</i>	Jarrah	Tree	Myrtaceae	12, 66, 67, 69, 100, 111, 124
<i>Eucalyptus patens</i>	Yarri	Tree	Myrtaceae	66
<i>Eucalyptus spp.</i>		Tree	Myrtaceae	1
<i>Eucalyptus wandoo</i>	Wandoo	Tree	Myrtaceae	11
<i>Fagus spp.</i>	Beech	Tree	Fagaceae	34
<i>Fagus sylvatica</i>	European beech	Tree	Fagaceae	6, 18, 84, 86, 92, 94, 116, 121
<i>Gentiana lutea</i>	Great yellow gentian	Herb / Forb	Gentianaceae	19
<i>Halimium commutatum</i>	Yellow rockrose	Shrub	Cistaceae	21
<i>Halimium halimifolium</i>	Rock rose	Shrub	Cistaceae	21
<i>Helichrysum italicum</i>	Curry plant	Shrub	Asteraceae	21
<i>Juniperus communis</i>	Common juniper	Shrub	Cupressaceae	48, 97
<i>Juniperus oxycedrus</i>	Prickly juniper	Tree	Cupressaceae	48
<i>Juniperus phoenicea</i>	Phoenicean juniper	Shrub	Cupressaceae	59
<i>Juniperus phoenicea</i> ssp. <i>turbinata</i>	Mediterranean juniper	Shrub	Cupressaceae	21
<i>Juniperus thurifera</i>	Spanish juniper	Tree	Cupressaceae	37
<i>Kageneckia angustifolia</i>	Frangel	Tree	Rosaceae	40

<i>Lavandula stoechas</i>	French lavender	Shrub	Lamiaceae	21
<i>Myrica californica</i>	Pacific wax myrtle	Shrub	Myricaceae	64
<i>Nothofagus glauca</i>	Hualo	Tree	Nothofagaceae	40
<i>Nothofagus macrocarpa</i>	Santiago's oak	Tree	Nothofagaceae	40, 119, 120
<i>Nothofagus obliqua</i>	Patagonian oak	Tree	Nothofagaceae	33
<i>Notholithocarpus densiflorus</i>	Tanoak	Tree	Fagaceae	64
<i>Pelargonium</i> spp.		Shrub, herb, geophyte	Geraniaceae	127
<i>Phillyrea latifolia</i>	Mock privet	Tree	Oleaceae	92
<i>Pinus albicaulis</i>	Whitebark	Tree	Pinaceae	23
<i>Pinus cembra</i>	Swiss pine	Tree	Pinaceae	108
<i>Pinus contorta</i>	Lodgepole pine	Tree	Pinaceae	23
<i>Pinus flexilis</i>	Limber pine	Tree	Pinaceae	110
<i>Pinus halepensis</i>	Aleppo pine	Tree	Pinaceae	14, 16, 34, 38, 39, 41, 106, 108
<i>Pinus jeffreyi</i>	Jeffrey's pine	Tree	Pinaceae	23
<i>Pinus lambertiana</i>	Sugar pine	Tree	Pinaceae	9, 27, 112
<i>Pinus leucodermis</i>	Bosnian pine	Tree	Pinaceae	18
<i>Pinus longaeva</i>	Great Basin Bristlecone pine	Tree	Pinaceae	110
<i>Pinus monticola</i>	Western white pine	Tree	Pinaceae	23
<i>Pinus nigra</i>	Black pine	Tree	Pinaceae	16, 28, 29, 34, 41, 48, 93, 106
<i>Pinus pinaster</i>	Maritime pine	Tree	Pinaceae	1, 5, 15, 74
<i>Pinus pinea</i>	Stone pine	Tree	Pinaceae	1, 16, 21

<i>Pinus ponderosa</i>	Ponderosa pine	Tree	Pinaceae	9, 27, 112
<i>Pinus</i> spp.		Tree	Pinaceae	44, 70
<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>	Scots pine	Tree	Pinaceae	2, 6, 14, 16, 34, 41, 48, 106
<i>Pinus uncinata</i>	Mountain pine	Tree	Pinaceae	41
<i>Proustia cuneifolia</i>	Huañil	Shrub	Asteraceae	40
<i>Pseudotsuga menziesii</i>	Douglas fir	Tree	Pinaceae	9, 64
<i>Quercus agrifolia</i>	California live oak	Tree	Fagaceae	64
<i>Quercus cerris</i>	Turkey oak	Tree	Fagaceae	18
<i>Quercus chrysolepis</i>	Canyon live oak	Tree	Fagaceae	27
<i>Quercus faginea</i>	Portuguese oak	Tree	Fagaceae	28, 29
<i>Quercus ilex</i>	Holm oak	Tree	Fagaceae	2, 13, 16, 29, 31, 32, 34, 35, 56, 63, 73, 75, 84, 86, 105
<i>Quercus kelloggii</i>	California black oak	Tree	Fagaceae	112
<i>Quercus petraea</i>	Sessile oak	Tree	Fagaceae	86
<i>Quercus pubescens</i>	Downy oak	Tree	Fagaceae	92
<i>Quercus pyrenaica</i>	Pyrenean oak	Tree	Fagaceae	46
<i>Quercus robur</i>	Pedunculate oak	Tree	Fagaceae	1, 46
<i>Quercus rotundifolia</i>	Holm oak	Tree	Fagaceae	1
<i>Quercus</i> spp.	Oak	Tree	Fagaceae	4, 16, 70, 87, 95
<i>Quercus suber</i>	Cork oak	Tree	Fagaceae	1
<i>Quercus subpyrenaica</i>	Downy oak	Tree	Fagaceae	83
<i>Rhamnus ludovici-salvatoris</i>	Balearic Island buckthorn	Shrub	Rhamnaceae	55

<i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i>	Rosemary	Shrub	Lamiaceae	21
<i>Sequoia sempervirens</i>	Coastal redwood	Tree	Cupressaceae	64
<i>Spartium junceum</i>	Spanish broom	Shrub	Fabaceae	92
<i>Thymus mastichina</i>	Spanish marjoram	Shrub	Lamiaceae	21
<i>Tsuga mertensiana</i>	Mountain hemlock	Tree	Pinaceae	23
<i>Ulex australis</i>	Gorse	Shrub	Fabaceae	21
<i>Widdringtonia cedarbergensis</i>	Clanwilliam cedar	Tree	Cupressaceae	126

* Publication references follow the numerical order as appears in the full publication list in Dataset S1.

Dataset S1. Excel workbook (“Dataset_1_Themes.xlsx”) containing four (4) spreadsheets, two of which correspond to the .csv files required for the analysis. The .csv files are provided independently as Datasets S2 - S3.

Dataset S2. Comma separated values file (“themes_expanded.csv”) containing thematic data for visualising trends in responses across regions.

Dataset S3. Comma separated values file (“ci_scores.csv”) containing confidence index scores for each publication.

Dataset S4. Quarto Markdown document (“Dataset_1_Themes.qmd”) containing the full thematic analysis workflow.

Dataset S5. PDF (“Dataset_1_Themes.pdf”) containing the output of the associated Quarto Markdown document.

SI References

1. M. I. O’Connor, *et al.*, Strengthening confidence in climate change impact science. *Global Ecology and Biogeography* **24**, 64–76 (2015).
2. K. Konno, B. Livoreil, A. S. Pullin, *Collaboration for Environmental Evidence Critical Appraisal Tool: Version 0.3*. (Collaboration for Environmental Evidence, 2021).